

Response of rainfed lowland rice varieties to different N levels under two types of water management

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Low-yielding traditional rice varieties (1.5-2.5 t ha⁻¹) are cultivated on 820,000 ha of coastal areas in India. After recurrent selection for six generations, six advanced-generation varieties for shallow and semideep submergence water regimes were identified as promising. We evaluated the yield response of these varieties to different N levels to identify the optimum N dose under two water management conditions.

The field experiment was conducted at the CSSRI RRS in a replicated (three) split-plot design from 1994-95 to 1996-97 with six varieties (Table 1), each under shallow (15-25 cm) and deep (25-50 cm) submergence in the main plot and six levels of N (0, 20, 40, 60, 80, and 100 kg ha⁻¹) in the subplot. Soil at the experimental site was clay loam with pH 6.8 and an EC of 5.53 dS m⁻¹. The soil contained 280-295 kg available N ha⁻¹, alkaline KMnO₄ extractable (high); 20 kg Olsen P ha⁻¹, NaHCO₃ extractable (medium); and 182 kg K ha⁻¹, NH₄OAc extractable (medium). CSR1 (av yield, 3.0 t ha⁻¹) and SR26B (av yield, 2.5 t ha⁻¹) were used as checks for screening under shallow and semideep submergence, respectively. Based on grain yield of each variety at different N levels pooled over the years, quadratic response functions were fitted and optimum N levels were determined.

Under shallow submergence, CST7-1 yielded more than the other varieties except for CSRC(S)-11-4-4-1 (Table 1). These two varieties registered an average 37% increase in grain yield over local check CSR1. Grain yields of IR16294 CS-9-1, C200-BS-6-23, and CSRC(S)14-1-B-0 were significantly higher than that of the check. The maximum grain yield under semideep waterlogged conditions was observed in

CSRC(D) 4-3-0, which outyielded the check by 43%. C300-BD-50-11, C99-BD-9-26, C340-22-17, and C340-22-5 yielded on a par with each other. Even the lowest yield of CSRC(D)13-12-2-1 was higher by 31% than the check's yield. Although maximum grain yields were generally achieved with 80 kg N ha⁻¹, the response to fertilizer was significant only up to 60 kg ha⁻¹ under both water management conditions. N levels beyond 80 kg ha⁻¹ decreased rice yield. The optimum N levels varied between 34-48 kg ha⁻¹ under shallow submergence and 26-38 kg ha⁻¹ under semideep submergence (Table 2). Under shallow submergence, although average yield was high for CST7-1 and CSRC(S)11-4-4-1, agronomic N-use efficiency was highest for IR16294-CS-9-1, followed by

CST7-1. C340-22-5 had the best agronomic N-use efficiency under semideep submerged conditions. Response to N fertilizers, yields, and agronomic N-use efficiency were higher under shallow submergence than under semideep submergence. Poor crop growth coupled with low tillering ability under waterlogged conditions may have resulted in a low response to N fertilizers.

Thus, considering yield and agronomic N-use efficiency, CST7-1 and IR16294-CS-9-1 under shallow submergence and C340-22-5 and CSRC(D)-4-3-0 under semideep conditions may be recommended for cultivation in the low-lying coastal areas in India.

Table 1. Grain yield (t ha⁻¹) of advanced-generation rice varieties under different N levels and two different water management scenarios (pooled over 3 yr).

Variety	N levels (kg ha ⁻¹)						Mean
	0	20	40	60	80	100	
<i>Shallow submergence (15-25 cm)</i>							
CST7-1	3.4	3.6	4.0	4.7	4.7	4.5	4.2
IR16294-CS-9-1	2.7	3.2	3.4	4.0	4.2	3.8	3.5
C200-BS-6-23	2.2	2.7	3.4	4.0	4.1	4.0	3.4
CSRC(S)5-2-25	2.4	2.7	3.0	3.3	3.8	3.5	3.2
CSRC(S)14-1-B-0	2.8	3.2	3.4	4.0	4.2	4.0	3.6
CSRC(S)11-4-4-1	3.0	3.5	4.1	4.5	4.6	4.5	4.0
Mean	2.8	3.2	3.5	4.0	4.3	4.1	
LSD (P = 0.05) Variety 0.47, N 0.34, V × N not significant							
<i>Semideep submergence (25-50 cm)</i>							
C300-BD-50-11	2.8	3.1	3.4	3.7	4.0	3.5	3.4
C99-BD-9-26	2.7	3.2	3.5	3.6	3.8	3.7	3.4
CSRC(D)4-3-0	2.7	3.1	3.7	3.9	4.0	4.0	3.6
CSRC(D)13-12-2-1	2.5	2.9	3.4	3.6	3.7	3.7	3.3
C340-22-5	2.2	2.9	3.6	3.8	4.0	3.9	3.4
C340-22-17	2.4	2.9	3.5	3.8	4.1	4.0	3.4
Mean	2.5	3.0	3.5	3.8	3.9	3.8	
LSD (P = 0.05) Variety 0.35, N 0.23, V × N not significant							

Table 2. N response and agronomic N-use efficiency of different rice varieties.

Variety	Response function ^a	R ²	Optimum N dose (kg ha ⁻¹)	Grain yield at optimum N dose (t ha ⁻¹)	Agronomic N-use efficiency (kg ha ⁻¹)
<i>Shallow submergence (15-25 cm)</i>					
CST7-1	Y = 3492 + 11.45 x - 0.0165x ²	0.874	48.0	4.0	10.62
IR16294-CS-9-1	Y = 2563 + 10.84 x - 0.0160x ²	0.847	44.7	3.4	12.01
C200-BS-6-23	Y = 2845 + 09.57 x - 0.0175x ²	0.887	38.0	3.2	8.95
CSRC(S)5-2-25	Y = 2562 + 09.43 x - 0.0142x ²	0.871	34.0	2.9	9.11
CSRC(S)14-1-B-0	Y = 2895 + 09.85 x - 0.0147x ²	0.900	36.5	3.2	9.31
CSRC(S)11-4-4-1	Y = 3165 + 10.15 x - 0.0131x ²	0.815	41.6	3.6	9.85
<i>Semideep submergence (25-50 cm)</i>					
C300-BD-50-11	Y = 2840 + 09.67 x - 0.0175x ²	0.801	25.7	3.1	9.73
C99-BD-9-26	Y = 2685 + 09.75 x - 1.0157x ²	0.811	34.0	3.0	9.41
CSRC(D)4-3-0	Y = 2705 + 10.51 x - 0.0178x ²	0.890	37.6	3.1	9.84
CSRC(D)13-12-2-1	Y = 2512 + 09.14 x - 0.0185x ²	0.847	36.7	3.1	9.26
C340-22-5	Y = 2125 + 10.52 x - 0.0114x ²	0.878	26.6	2.4	10.34
C340-22-17	Y = 2401 + 09.65 x - 0.0100x ²	0.844	28.0	2.7	9.64

^aY in kg ha⁻¹.

Influence of organic, biofertilizer, and inorganic forms of nitrogen on rice quality

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We studied the complementary effect of organic and inorganic N along with biological N sources (*Azospirillum*) on rice quality. A field experiment with dry-season (kuruvai) rice (June-September) was conducted in 1996 and 1997.

Forty-five-day-old daincha (*Sesbania aculeata*) at 12 t ha⁻¹ and sunn hemp (*Crotalaria juncea*) at 11 t ha⁻¹ were incorporated *in situ* 3 d before rice transplanting. Farmyard manure was applied at 12.5 t ha⁻¹ at the start of first puddling. Rice was inoculated with *Azospirillum* through seed treatment (600 g ha⁻¹), seedling dip (100 g ha⁻¹), and soil application (200 g ha⁻¹). Considering the recommended dose of inorganic fertilizer of 150-50-50 kg NPK ha⁻¹, various proportions of mineral N (50%, 75%, and 100% of recommended N) were applied to account for the complementary effect of N from organic and biofertilizer forms.

Proper N nutrition and favorable soil conditions due to organic fertilizers and biofertilizers ensured the nutrient supply to the crop and improved the quality of rice grain. Incorporation of organic fertilizers and inoculation of *Azospirillum* along with application of inorganic N significantly increased optimum cooking time, lowered gruel loss, and improved total amylose and crude protein contents (see table). Among the organic fertilizers, daincha enhanced the quality characters

of rice best. Elongation ratio, however, was not influenced by the treatments. Incorporation of daincha at 12 t ha⁻¹ and application of 50% of recommended inorganic N plus *Azospirillum* inoculation improved rice quality.

Effect of N management on quality of rice^a.

Treatment	Optimum cooking time (min)	Elongation ratio	Gruel loss (%)	Total amylose content (%)	Crude protein (%)
<i>Organic fertilizers</i>					
M ₁ = control	14.6	1.41	3.9	25.2	7.8
M ₂ = FYM	16.2	1.42	3.6	26.4	8.3
M ₃ = daincha	17.2	1.46	3.1	28.4	9.2
M ₄ = sunn hemp	16.7	1.45	3.3	27.2	8.3
SE	0.3	0.03	0.06	0.3	0.13
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.7	ns	0.15	0.8	0.31
<i>Inorganic and biofertilizers</i>					
S ₁ = 50% N	14.4	1.42	3.1	24.9	7.8
S ₂ = 75% N	15.1	1.43	3.6	25.7	8.1
S ₃ = 100% N	16.0	1.44	4.1	26.6	8.5
S ₄ = 50% N + Azos	16.9	1.46	2.9	28.6	9.3
S ₅ = 75% N + Azos	17.2	1.46	3.4	27.8	8.9
S ₆ = 100% N + Azos	17.5	1.44	3.9	27.0	8.6
SE	0.32	0.04	0.05	0.31	0.11
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.65	ns	0.11	0.64	0.23

^aN = nitrogen, Azos = *Azospirillum*, FYM = farmyard manure, SE = standard error, LSD = least significant differences, ns = not significant.